

Contribution Of Leadership Training In Improving Financial Aspects Of Schools Heads In Punjab

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>The present study was conducted to evaluate the contribution of Promotion-Linked Training for improving financial aspects of secondary school heads in Punjab. Main objective of the study was to evaluate the contribution of leadership training for improving financial aspects of secondary school heads in Punjab. All secondary school head teachers (295) were the population of the study. For the purpose 30 head teachers were selected randomly as sample of the study. The data were collected through self-developed questionnaire having fifteen statements on Likert scale. It was validated by five educationists and pilot tested from 30 respondents. It was found reliable. The researcher collected the data personally. Data collection rate was 100%. It was concluded that PLT is not effective as preparation of school budget was not discussed in the training. It was also found that activities related to school budget were not practiced in the training. It was recommended that there should be activities based training for secondary school heads. Head teachers may be enabled to prepare school budget. Proper preference should be given to Non-Salary Budget and audit handling reports.</i></p>
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Introduction

Leadership plays a vital role in any organization. Training enriches the performance of a leader. There are different trainings for educational leaders in Punjab. Promotion-linked training is a type of leadership training. It is an in-service training for leadership development. The purpose of this training is to improve the quality of working employees. Punjab School Education (SED) department is one of the main departments working under the control of Government of the Punjab. There are different levels of schools in Punjab. These are known as; Primary schools, Elementary schools, Secondary schools, and Higher secondary schools (SED Punjab).

Schools are social institutions. These are centers for learning and learners. Secondary schools are mostly situated at the center of the area. Generally, most of the people have to interact with teachers of secondary school especially their head teachers. There are two modes for the selection of head teachers in Punjab. These are mentioned in the following:

1. Head teachers selected through Punjab Public Service Commission, Lahore
2. Head teachers promoted through in-service quota

According to the promotion policy 2010, 33% secondary school teachers are selected through Punjab Public Service Commission, Lahore while 67% secondary school teachers are promoted as head teachers through in-service quota (Government of the Punjab Notification No. SOR-III(S&GAD)1-19/2004(P) dated 14th March 2014)

According to the promotion policy 2010 secondary school teachers who are promoted through in-service quota have to participate in the training which is called Promotion-Linked Training. This training is imparted through Quaid-e-Azam Academy for Educational Development in all over the Punjab. The main aim of this training is to prepare head teachers for future responsibilities. (Government of the Punjab Notification No. SOR-III(S&GAD)1-19/2004(P) dated 14th March 2014)

Head teachers of secondary schools have to play different roles in the schools. They have to maintain the discipline of the school. They have to interact with teachers, students, parents and community. Head teachers are responsible for preparing young generation to meet the challenges of the future. Head teachers have to maintain all the activities in school. They have to focus on the academic achievements of the students. They have to mentor, monitor and guide the teachers. Head teachers have to maintain and manage financial resources of the school. Knowledge of certain financial aspects is necessary for head teachers. Some of them are: maintaining cash book, acquaintance roll, school budget, contingencies grants, pension rules, TA/DA rules,

Non-Salary Budget, Audit handling reports, source generation techniques, Head teacher's role as drawing and disbursing officer and knowledge of PPRA rules.

Objectives of the Study

Objective of the study were:

1. To investigate the contributions of Promotion-Linked Training in enabling school heads to prepare budget for school.
2. To find out the worth of PLT in term of teaching pension rules for school heads.
3. To Assess the PLT to train the schools head for utilization of Farough-e- Talim funds
4. To examine the PLT in understanding the Punjab Procurement Regulatory Authority rules for Secondary School Heads.

Research Questions for the Study

Following were the research questions for the study:

1. What are the contributions of Promotion-Linked Training in enabling schools' heads to prepare budget for school?
2. What is the worth of Non-Salary Budget and pension rules for secondary school heads?
3. What is the importance of source generation techniques for secondary school heads?
4. What is the significance of Punjab Procurement Regulatory Authority rules for secondary school heads?

Delimitation of the Study

The study was delimited to the following Government Secondary Schools of Rawalpindi District.

Review of Related Literature

Secondary education is an important part of education. According to Suleman (2015) secondary education occupies a strategic position in the national education system. The secondary school is an institution or a human industry which is set up for improving individuals in terms of skills, behaviors and all round qualities and excellence.

1. Importance of secondary education

In Pakistan secondary education is considered as a base for higher education. It is also terminal stage for most of the students. Secondary education consists of two stages, secondary and higher secondary. The duration of secondary education is four years. At the end of each year annual examination is conducted by the concerned board of Intermediate and Secondary Education (BISE). Medium of instruction is Urdu in public sector schools. There are different groups at secondary level. There are different subjects at secondary level. These subjects are further divided into compulsory and elective. Students are given choice to select the subjects of their choice. Raja (2000) describes that secondary education is an important sub-sector of the whole education system. Therefore, secondary education is considered an important sector of the education.

2. Secondary School Heads as Educational Leaders

Head teachers play an important role in education system. Head teachers play a vital role in improving secondary education. They play leadership role in secondary education. Tahira (2005) states that head teachers or principals occupy the most important position and considered as foundation stone in the administration of school. Head teachers are bride among teachers, students, parents and planners. Suleman, et al. (2012) state that effective administration and management plays a crucial role in strengthening the activities of an organization, association or institution.

3. Head teachers and their designations

In Punjab head teachers have different designations based on their scales. The detail of head teachers' designations is in the following:

1. Headmaster (Working in BPS-17)
2. Senior headmaster (Working in BPS-18)
3. Principal (Working in BPS-19 and BPS-20)

Most of the head teachers are appointed or promoted in BPS 17, then after some time they are promoted as senior headmaster in BPS 18 on the basis of seniority cum fitness. After this again they are promoted in BPS 19 and then in BPS 20.

4. Mode of selection

There are following modes of selection of head teachers in Punjab.

1. Promotees

In Punjab secondary school teachers are working in BPS 16. The qualification of secondary school teacher (SST) is M.A. B.Ed. When secondary school teachers reached in the promotion zone they are required to participate in Promotion Link Training. It is mandatory for all the teachers in BPS-16 to BPS-20. This training is arranged by the Punjab School Education Department and Quaid-e-Azam Academy for Educational Development (QAED) concerned. According to Punjab School Education Department (SED) 67 % SSTs are promoted as head teachers on the basis of seniority cum fitness.

2. Direct Selectees

Head teachers selected by the Punjab Public Service Commission (PPSC), Lahore are called direct selectees. According to the promotion policy 2010 Government of the Punjab (GOP) 33% head teachers are selected by the PPSC, Lahore. PPSC gives advertisement in the daily national newspapers in which their qualification and requirements are mentioned in detailed.

5. Role and responsibilities of head teachers

According to Newstorm (2007) leadership is a process to instigate others to work in order to obtain the objectives. Head teachers play the role of leaders in secondary schools. There are different roles and responsibilities of head teachers. Some are described by The Wallace Foundation (2013) as stated below:

1. Shaping a vision of academic success for all students
2. Creating a climate hospitable to education
3. Cultivating leadership in others
4. Improving instruction
5. Managing people, data and processes to foster school improvement

In short, school leader has a vision to improve the whole school by using different sources. He creates conducive environment. The head teachers have to manage people, data and processes for school improvement. There are different types of leadership known as autocratic leaders, democratic leaders and laissez fair leaders. The head teachers work for the betterment of the institutions according to their own styles. These styles reflect from the decisions and performance of the head teachers. There is a need of training to polish their skills and attitude.

6. Need of training for head teachers

According to Scheerens, (2010) there is a need of training for head teachers as continuous changes are happening in all walks of life. Head teachers play an important role in improving the quality of education. They are bridge between planners and practitioners. Leadership training is compulsory before their placement as head teacher. According to Aremides (2003) head teacher must receive training to fulfill the following needs:

1. Sufficient academic and professional qualification;
2. A sound knowledge of the techniques and methodologies of educational practices.
3. A capability to provide professional leadership to all sections of the school community;
4. An understanding of the interdependence of the different sections of the school community;
5. An understanding of school finance and accounting procedures;

The above quotation shows the need of training for head teachers. There are different areas in which training is needed to the head teachers. Some important areas are highlighted in the abovementioned quotation. Keeping in view the need of training for head teachers Government of the Punjab started such type of training which enhances their leadership skills to strengthen secondary education in Punjab. The name of this training is Promotion-Link Training. It is one of the leadership trainings.

7. Training and its types

Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary expresses training as the process of learning the skills that you need to do a job. It enhances the knowledge, skills and capacities of the employees. According to Chandramohan (2007, p.12) states that training enhances six C, s i.e.; Competence, Commitment, Creativity, Confidence, Contribution, Communications, and six E, s i.e. Efficiency, Effectiveness, Etiquette, Emotional stability, Emotional intelligence and Empowerment. In short, training increases the knowledge of the employees. It enhances the hidden abilities and skills of the employees. There are certain benefits of training. The main benefit of the training is to prepare skillful employees for the organization. It enhances their performance of the employees of the organization. There are different types of training on the bases of their objectives.

8. Types of Training

There are different types of trainings. Some of them are mentioned in the following:

1. Pre-service Training

Pre-service Training is given to the persons who intend to join that particular profession. In teaching there are different Pre-service Trainings that are given to the teachers according to their qualification and level of teaching, some the important Pre-service Trainings are mentioned in the following;

- a) Primary Teaching Certificate (PTC)
- b) Certificate in Teaching (CT)
- c) B.ED (Elementary, Secondary, Early Child)
- d) BSED (Bachelor in Science Education)
- e) M.Ed (Elementary, Secondary, Special Education, Science Education and Education Planning and Management (EPM)

2. Induction Training

Induction training is given to the employees before starting their jobs. In this training employee are taught certain rules and regulation about the service. The purpose of this training is to prepare employees to meet the challenges of future. In Punjab School Education Department induction training is compulsory for all the

teachers and head teachers. Every teacher has to attend induction training after their recruitment. This training is imparted to the newly recruited teachers and head teachers under the instructions of Quaid-e-Azam Academy for Educational Development and Government of the Punjab School Education Department. (Government of the Punjab Notification No. SOR-III(S&GAD)1-19/2004(P) dated 14th March 2014)

3. In-service Training

In-service training is given to the employees during the service. The purpose of this training is to enhance the capacity of the employees. In-service training plays vital role in improving knowledge, skills and abilities of the employees. According to Hussain (2011) in-service training provided to secondary school heads for their professional growth and enhancing instructional efficiency, should result in maximum output with minimum resources. In-service training helps in polishing the abilities of the leaders.

Types of in-service training

1. Refresher courses
2. Seminars
3. Workshops
4. Conferences
5. Promotion-Linked Training

17. Promotion-Linked Training (PLT)

Promotion-Linked Training is a type of in-service training. The Government of the Punjab notified on 29th March 2014 making mandatory to attend training for promotion in the next grade for all serving teachers/officers of school education department. Directorate of Staff Development presently renamed as Quaid-e-Azam Academy for Educational Development being an apex organization first training session under promotion policy 2010. Training Need Assessment (TNA) was conducted by the officers/teachers. The purpose of the training was to prepare efficient and effective leadership for secondary schools in the Punjab. The duration of the training was four weeks for the officer/teachers working in BPS 16 to BPS-20. (GOP Report 2014 on Promotion-Linked Training of SS/HM (BPS 17).

Secondary School Teachers (SSTs) are promoted as head teachers on the bases of their seniority cum fitness through in-service quota. According to Promotion Policy 2010 Secondary School teachers are promoted as head teacher out of 67 % in-service quota reserved for the in-service teachers. Those who are promoted through in-service quota they have to attend Promotion-Linked Training to enhance their capabilities as head teachers. Promotion-Linked Training is mandatory for teachers promoting in the next grade. In Punjab, Promotion-Linked Training is given 15 % weightage for promotion. There are different quotas for promotion of in-service teachers. The promotees head teachers need training to improve their knowledge, skills and abilities to perform their responsibilities. (Promotion Policy 2010)

18. Importance of Promotion-Linked Training

Promotion-Linked Training is mandatory for secondary school heads. Head teachers who were previously performing their duties as teachers in the institutions which is entirely different from their present nature of job. Teaching is different from administration. They have to play the role of an educational leader. They have to deal with teaching and non-teaching staff. They have to play the role of mentor, monitor, supervise, guide and a counselor in the institutions. They have to act as a drawing and disbursing officer of the institutions. They get awareness about their roles and responsibilities through leadership training. Therefore, Promotion-Linked Training is necessary for future leaders of the institution. It is their need. It helps them in enhancing their different skills such as financial skills.

19. Objectives of Promotion Link Training

There are different objectives of Promotion-Linked Training. Some important are mentioned by Quaid-e-Azam Academy for Educational Development, Lahore (QAED) previously known as Directorate of Staff Development, Lahore (DSD). According to the report (2014) of Promotion-Linked Training these are in the following;

1. To polish their leadership qualities and put efforts to bring revolutionary change in them
2. To acquainted them with working norms, roles and responsibilities, rules of business, code of conduct and discipline required at elevated level
3. To apply all the possible gadgets to polish their skills and to make them as pro-active member/leader in the educational sector's public community
4. To provide the participants an opportunity to practically implement the knowledge skillfully in field
5. To bring about an attitudinal change in them to ensure their working is more scientific, objective, transparent, accountable and participatory
6. To enhance skills in ICT, Presentation & communication skills and in report writing.

The above mentioned objectives of Promotion-Linked Training were designed by Directorate of Staff Development presently known as Quaid-e-Azam Academy for Educational Development (QAED) which was an apex organization of the Government of the Punjab. The objectives set by the above mentioned organization

were comprehensive in nature. In this research article we have to look at different financial aspects of Promotion-Linked Training whether it is fulfilling all the areas of financial aspects of leadership or it need to improve it.

20. Financial Aspects of Promotion Linked-Training

Knowledge of financial aspects of Promotion-Linked Training is considered key achievement for heads of secondary school teachers. There are several financial aspects of Promotion-linked training. Some important financial aspects are mentioned in the following.

1. Preparation of school budget

School budget is an important document of school record. It is prepared annually by the Drawing and Disbursing Officer (DDO) of the institution. Head teacher being the DDO of the institution prepares this document. All the expected expenditures of the institution are showed through this document.

2. Pension rules

In every institution there are many employees serving under the control of the head of the institution. There are certain employees who want to retire from service after completing 25 years of service. Some other wants to get retirement after superannuation. There are different rules for pension. Head teacher being Drawing and Disbursing Officer (DDO) of the institution have to prepare pension cases of the employees of working under his control.

3. Non-Salary Budget (NSB) utilization

According to the Government of the Punjab there are three types of budget.

1. Salary Budget

2. Non-Salary Budget

3. Developmental Budget

Non-Salary Budget is allocated to schools according to the strength of the students. It is transferred to the school on quarterly basis. There are certain rules to spend NSB for the welfare of the students. There are restrictions which head teacher has to keep in mind before spending Non-Salary Budget.

4. Audit handling reports

Government institutions are granted different grants by the Government under different heads. There is a proper procedure to spend these grants. Proper documentation is also necessary for the income and expenditure. There is a proper procedure of audits for the Government institution. Head teachers have to handle audit reports.

5. Source generation techniques

Source generation techniques are necessary for a head teacher. In the present era head teacher has to know about the different techniques of source generation. Schools are social centre. Head teacher involves community for the betterment of the institution.

6. Farog-E-Taleem Fund(FTF)

Farog-E-Taleem Funds are collected by the students. There are certain rules and regulation to spend Farog-E-Taleem Fund for the welfare of the students. Head teacher being Drawing and Disbursing Officer of the institution should know the rules to spend the fund.

7. Punjab Delegation of Finance Power rules 2006

Head teachers being the Drawing and Disbursing Officers should know about their powers. Government delegated certain powers to the head teachers working under Punjab School Education Department.

8. Physical Assets

There are different assets of Government institution. Physical assets include land, building, tools, plants, machinery and vehicles etc. knowledge of physical assets of the institution is necessary for the head teachers.

9. Auction of Government Assets

There are certain rules for auction of Government assets. Head of the institution should know the rules and regulations of the auction. He should know the proper procedure of the auction. Then income should be deposited in the government treasure through proper procedure.

10. PPRA rules

PPRA stands for Punjab Procurement Regulatory Authority. Knowledge of PPRA rules is important for the head of an institution. There are certain things required to purchase for the best of the institution. Knowledge of required documents and procedures is important for the head teachers. Head teachers have to purchase different items keeping in view certain rules and regulations. (Punjab Procurement Rules 2014)

Research Methodology

The study was descriptive by nature. Therefore, survey method was used to collect the data.

Population

The population of the study was Ninety four (94) Secondary schools' heads working in Secondary Schools of Rawalpindi-Punjab.

Sample

Thirty (30) head teachers working in Public Secondary Schools of Rawalpindi, Punjab were selected randomly as sample of the study.

Research Instruments

The researcher used Questionnaire of Five point rating scales to collect the data from the sample of the study. There were two parts of the questionnaire. The first part was related to personal information of the respondents. The second part consists of 16 statements.

Validation of the Research Instrument

After getting the opinions of the experts the research instruments were validated.

Pilot Testing of the Research Instrument

Research instrument was pilot tested on 5 head teachers of secondary school which were not included in the sample of the study. After pilot testing the research instrument was finalized.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

The reliability of the instruments for head teachers and secondary school teachers was calculated by using Cronbach alpha. It was 0.91 which indicated that the questionnaire is highly reliable.

Data Collection

The data were collected using five points Likert scales from 30 head teachers of Public Secondary schools of District Rawalpindi personally by the researcher and through email as well.

Data Analysis

Collected data were tabulated item wise. After this data were analyzed by using simple percentage and mean of the items. Data were analysed with the help of 13 tables which are as under;

Table 1 Preparation of School budget was discussed in the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	7	6	1	10	6	30	2.9
Percentage	23.3	20.0	3.3	33.3	20	100	

Table 1 shows that 43.3% head teachers agreed while 53.3% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M=2.9$ which indicates that majority of trainees viewed that preparation of school budget was not discussed in the training.

Table 2 Activities related to School budget were practised during the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	7	5	1	9	8	30	2.8
Percentage	23.3	16.7	3.3	30	26.7	100	

Table 2 shows that 40% head teachers viewed that activities related to school budget were practiced during training of head teachers while 56.7% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M=2.8$ which indicates that majority of the trainees held opinion that the leadership training failed in conducting activities related to school budget.

Table 3 Trainees were enabled to prepare budget for school

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	6	7	1	13	3	30	3.0
Percentage	20	23.3	3.3	43.3	10	100	

Table 3 shows that 43.3% head teachers viewed that training enabled trainees to prepare budget for school while 53.3% of disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M=3.0$ which indicates that majority of head teachers opinioned that training failed in enabling trainees to prepare budget for school.

Table 4 Techniques to utilize Non-salary budget were discussed in the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	4	7	1	14	4	30	2.8
Percentage	13.3	23.3	3.3	46.6	13.3	100	

Table 4 shows that 36.6% head teachers viewed that techniques to utilize Non-salary budget were discussed in the training while 59.9% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is M= 2.8 which indicates that majority of head teachers opinioned that training failed in enabling trainees to utilize Non-salary budget.

Table 5 Activities were arranged to use Non-salary budget

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	5	8	1	12	4	30	2.9
Percentage	16.7	26.7	3.3	40	13.3	100	

Table 5 shows that 43.4% of head teachers opinioned that activities were arranged to use Non-salary budget while 53.3% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is M= 2.9 which indicates that majority of head teachers opinioned that in leadership training activities were not arranged to use Non-salary budget.

Table 6 Pension rules were shared in PLT

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	6	7	1	13	3	30	3.0
Percentage	20	23.3	3.3	43.3	10	100	

Table 6 shows that 43.3% of head teachers viewed that pension rules were shared in promotion-linked training while 53.3% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is M= 3.0 which indicates that a simple majority of head teachers held opinion that the training failed in sharing pension rules to the trainees.

Table 7 Activities related to pension rules were practised in the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	6	7	1	13	3	30	2.9
Percentage	16.7	26.7	3.3	43.3	10	100	

Table 7 shows that 43.4% of head teachers viewed that activities related to pension rules were practiced in the training while 53.3% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is M= 2.9 which indicates that simple majority of head teachers held opinion that promotion-linked training failed in conducting activities related to pension rules.

Table 8 Techniques to use Farooq-E-Taleem were shared in the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	12	12	1	3	2	30	4.0
Percentage	40	40	3.3	10	6.7	100	

Table 8 shows that 80% of head teachers viewed that techniques to use Farooq-E-Taleem were shared in the training while 16.7% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is M= 4.0 which indicates that significant majority of head teachers opinioned that training enabled trainees to use Farooq-E-Taleem.

Table 9 Activities related to Farooq-E-Taleem were shared in the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	10	11	1	4	4	30	3.6

Percentage	33.3	36.7	3.3	13.3	13.3	100	
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Table 9 shows that 70% of head teachers viewed that activities related to Farooq-E-Taleem were shared in the training while 26.6% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M= 3.6$ which indicates that significant majority of head teachers opinioned that activities related to Farooq-E-Taleem were shared in the training.

Table 10 Punjab Delegation of Finance Power rules 2006 were discussed in the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	7	6	1	10	6	30	2.9
Percentage	23.3	20	3.3	33.3	20	100	

Table 10 shows that 43.3% of head teachers viewed that Punjab Delegation of Finance Power rules 2006 were discussed in the training while 53.3% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M= 2.9$ which indicates that a simple majority of head teachers opinioned that Punjab Delegation of Finance Power rules 2006 were not discussed in the training. Therefore, head teachers held opinion that training did not enable head teachers to discuss Punjab Delegation of Finance Power rules 2006.

Table 11 Rules and regulations about physical assets were included in leadership training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	8	7	1	8	6	30	3.1
Percentage	26.7	23.3	3.3	26.7	20	100	

Table 11 shows that 50% of head teachers viewed that rules and regulations about physical assets were included in leadership training while 46.7% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M= 3.1$ which indicates that a majority of head teachers opinioned that rules and regulations about physical assets were included in leadership training.

Table 12 Proper procedure about auction of Government assets was included in the training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	8	5	2	9	6	30	3.0
Percentage	26.7	16.7	6.6	30	20	100	

Table 12 shows that 43.4% of head teachers agreed that proper procedure about auction of Government assets was included in the training while 50% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M= 3.0$ which indicates that a majority of head teachers opinioned that proper procedure about auction of Government assets was included in the training.

Table 13 PPRA rules were thoroughly discussed in the leadership training

Description	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Total	Mean Score
Frequency	5	6	1	8	10	30	2.6
Percentage	16.7	20	3.3	26.7	33.3	100	

Table 13 shows that 36.7% of head teachers agreed that PPRA rules were thoroughly discussed in the leadership training while 60% of respondents disagreed with the statement. The mean value is $M= 2.6$ which indicates that a majority of head teachers opinioned that PPRA rules were thoroughly discussed in the leadership training.

Results and Discussion

The study was conducted to evaluate the contribution of promotion-linked training. It was concluded that Promotion link training does not enable trainees to prepare budget for school activities related to school budget were not practiced during the training. The results are same in case of salary budget as well as non-salary budget. Sabir and Sadaf (2011) also found that head teachers of secondary school need training in preparing budget for school. No doubt, preparation of budget is major responsibility of administrator. Like other

administrator and manager, the school principal also has to prepare annual budget. It has two main heads, salary budget and non-salary budget. Therefore, knowledge of budget and its different head, authority of principal to utilize funds, is given to principals in training. Activity of preparation of budget is also part of this training so that principal can practically learn how to prepare the budget. But it is very alarming situation, that the Promotion link training fail to give the required knowledge as well as organizing activity. Its mean that PLT is not fruitful for school principals in this regard. Its clearly indicates that it is need of the hour to strengthen the PLT of teachers.

It was also found that knowledge and activities related to pension rules were not practised in the training. He or she has to prepare pension documents in their service. As it is well known that the teaching and non-teaching staff of our schools are regular employs and have right of pension. There are different types of pension like at completing 25 year of service, physical age of 60 or on medical ground at any stage of service. Therefore, knowledge of pension rules is necessary for head teachers. But unfortunately, it is not in practices in PLT which is question mark on the credibility of training.

Faroogh-e-Talim Fund is an important funds used for promotion of education. It is given by Punjab Government to schools head annually. It can be used on special cases and cannot be used in salary budget etc. It is auditable. So, knowledge and practice of its purpose and authority of its utilization is needed to head of school. But as the findings of the study showed that PLT is fail in this regard also.

Financial rules especially Punjab Delegation of Finance Power rules 2006 are important for secondary school heads. It was found that Punjab Delegation of Finance Power rules 2006 were not discussed in the training. It was also found that proper procedure about auction of Govt.assets was not included in the training. Furthermore, PPRA rules were not thoroughly discussed in the leadership training. As a result, the head teachers were not able to apply Punjab Procurement Regulatory Authority rules.

Recommendations

1. There should be activity-based training for head teachers of Public secondary schools.
2. Head teachers may be enabled to prepare budget for school and pension cases of teachers.
3. Proper preference should be given to Non-Salary Budget and Audit handling reports.
4. In head teachers' training practical activities should be arranged for utilization of Faroogh-e-Taleem Funds.
5. Punjab delegation of finance power rules 2006 and Procedure of auction of govt. assets.
6. Punjab Procurement Regulatory Authority (PPRA) rules and regulation about Donation should be given adequate preference in promotion-linked training.

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